

NEWSLETTER

Issue 15

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Editor's note:

This newsletter provides information of general interest on the activities of the SSSA Unit, including the CEO, ASTRON, AIR QUALITY and MOLAND projects, and is updated quarterly. It is supplementary to text which is also accessible within the CEO Home Page at:

<http://www.ceo.org/>

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INFEO

We are pleased to announce that INFEO went live as planned on 10 September. Release 1 of INFEO is now available at **<http://infeo.ceo.org/>**.

Through the launch of INFEO, the CEO is closer to realising its ideal of offering a one-stop shop for EO data and information. For the first time, users can now simultaneously search many data catalogues located across the world via a single user interface.

The simple Catalogue/Data search and the Adverts and Announcements system was completed and integrated into INFEO during July and August 1999. Operational testing of INFEO ran for one week in late August and changes have been made to the system based on the feedback received.

The following satellite data catalogues are currently searchable via INFEO:

- ARIS (Agricultural and Regional Information System) at the JRC
- ISIS (Intelligent Satellite Information System) at DLR
- EUROMAP at DLR
- MARF at EUMETSAT
- EURIMAGE
- SPOT
- HEOC (Hatoyama Earth Observation Center) at NASDA

Access is also offered to a map catalogue at IGN (Institut Geographique National) in France, an atmospheric catalogue at BADC (British Atmospheric Data Centre), as well as to land cover catalogues and environmental catalogues (for details see the EEIS project below).

The CEO is planning to host an INFEO workshop in February 2000. At this workshop the future of EO data and information systems will be discussed, as well as feedback from catalogue providers, and the expectations of future providers. If you would like to be sent further notification of this workshop, please contact Nina Costa via email: **nina.costa@jrc.it** or fax: +39 033278 5461.

EEIS PROJECT

European Environmental Information Services (EEIS)

In order to improve data interoperability between the two large user communities of Environment and Earth observation, the project 'European Environmental Information Services' was launched in early 1998.

EEIS bridges the gap between these two communities by linking their Internet-based information systems; the Catalogue of Data Sources (CDS) of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and INFEO, the CEO's search system for Earth observation data.

The main challenge of this project was to use the Catalogue Interoperability Protocol (CIP) to interconnect two radically different search systems (INFEO and WebCDS), as well as to connect two land cover catalogues to INFEO. The land cover catalogues in question are at the Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE) in the U.K. and at the Miljö Data Centrum (MDC) in Sweden. Although CIP was originally intended for EO users, it has been expanded to cover non-space data as well.

The EEIS service is new in that it will interconnect two already existing search systems for related user communities. An Environmental user will be thus be able to easily find earth observation data (e.g. satellite images) for their research and reports, and vice versa. It will be launched towards the end of 1999.

- Provision of seamless access to all information levels independent of their physical location.
- Access to ancillary information to both user communities.
- Provision of unique access to all information with a homogeneous user interface.
- Improvement regarding the use of the taxes paid by the citizen to avoid double development within the European Union (EU).
- Co-ordination of the ongoing work within the EU

For the latest information on this project please see the EEIS homepage at <http://eeis.ceo.sai.jrc.it/>. This project is being carried out by a consortium of 7 partners, details of which are also available on this web site.

CEO PROJECT UPDATE

SATWEB - Secure on-line data exchange through the WEB

Within one of the CEO's Product Development and Marketing contracts, a product known as SATWEB has been developed by euromap/GAF.

SATWEB is a first of its kind in the field of EO. Firstly it offers a fully automated ordering and delivery procedure for satellite data via the WWW. Secondly, the customer locates and only pays for the exact coverage that he or she requires. The data sets are sold on a square kilometre basis.

Delivered data sets are ortho-corrected to a commonly used map projection, and are ready for integration into hybrid GIS environments.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram explaining the EEIS project.

EEIS will provide unique access to both types of information within an homogenous user interface and without reducing the performance of any of two services. Each user community will be able to access the service via their 'own' search systems: Environmental users will be able access it via the locator system 'WebCDS'

(<http://www.mu.niedersachsen/system/cds>)

extended with new features to explore the data of remote sensing; Earth Observation users will be able access it via the INFEO search service (<http://info.ceo.org>).

In brief the benefits of EEIS are:

- Enhancement of environmental studies due to improved access to environmental and Earth Observation (EO) data.

Figure 2: Screen shot illustrating how a customer can select an area of interest and shows the estimated cost of the resulting data set.

Currently an IRS-1C-LISS mosaic of Germany is available with 25m resolution and in natural colour. The next country to be covered by this product is Austria. The mosaic itself has already been compiled and is scheduled to be launched on-line by the end of this year.

Figure 3: The dataset for a 15 x 20 km area around the mouth of the Ems River, north west of the city of Emden in Germany.

SATWEB is aimed at the following segments:

- 'Low-end' GIS users (e.g. urban planners)
- Desk top publishing companies
- Multimedia and WWW communities.

Image pricing, geocoding costs for satellite data, format problems and delivery times as well as the distribution scheme according to the path/row pattern, all represent obstacles that had prevented successful EO data sales to these groups in the past. SATWEB has overcome these and can be seen as the first step towards new satellite data delivery procedures which will meet the requirements of on-line customers in the 21st century.

SATWEB can be found at <http://satweb.gaf.de/>. For more information on this product, please contact Wolfgang Baetz at euromap via email baetz@gaf.de or fax: +49 (0)89 121528 79.

NEW PROJECT

ENVIP-Nature (ENVironmental Indicators for nature Protection) is a new project undertaken by the SSSA Unit. It started in January 1999 as part of the larger EURO-Landscape project and will continue over the next four years.

ENVIP-Nature concerns the definition and provision of a standard set of criteria, indicators and methods utilising Earth observation data and Geographic Information Systems for the characterisation, assessment and monitoring of European natural and semi-natural terrestrial landscapes with special emphasis on nature protection.

It adopts a landscape ecology approach and is based on the ecological network concept which consists of:

- Core areas to conserve ecosystems, habitats, species and landscapes;
- Biological corridors to improve the coherence of natural systems;
- Restoration areas to repair or restore damaged elements;
- Buffer zones to support and protect the network from adverse external influences.

The project primarily aims to support the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), particularly the European Biodiversity strategy (EBS, 1998) and the Pan-European Biological and Landscape Diversity Strategy (PEBLDS, 1995). It should provide transparent and harmonised information to meet the needs of policies such as the European Commission's Directive on the Conservation of Natural Habitats for the implementation of NATURA 2000, and also contribute to the objectives of the PEBLDS including the development of the Pan-European Ecological Network. The direct end-users are a variety of organisations responsible for environmental monitoring and nature protection activities.

ENVIP-Nature will contribute to the evaluation at the Pan-European level of the feasibility of establishing a common strategy for nature protection.

Pilot areas

The methodology will be assessed on pilot areas selected within the Member States and future associated CEEC countries. The areas include (1) natural and semi-natural terrestrial landscapes, ecosystems, habitats and species of European importance, (2) biotopes and legally protected sites through national or international instruments, and for the European Union also candidate sites for NATURA 2000, (3) all components of an ecological network.

Figure 4: Illustration of the biodiversity problem (Stern et al. 1980 and Melin 1995).

Current status

A set of representative areas belonging to different countries and biogeographic regions have been selected and SPOT4 XI, SPOT XS and Pan, IRS 1C Pan images have been acquired for all these areas. A one-year study addressing the role of high resolution satellite images for the definition of Landscape typology and indicators for nature protection will start within the framework of ENVIP-Nature at the end of 1999.

For further information on ENVIP-Nature, contact Christine Estreguil via email: christine.estreguil@jrc.it or fax: +39 033278 5461.

MAUVE PROJECT

The SSSA Unit participates in the MAUVE project, a Pilot Project in the Environment and Climate Programme of the 4th Framework Programme. The project is co-ordinated by the Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy and managed by DG Research. The main objective of MAUVE is to establish satellite-derived maps of surface Ultra-Violet (UV) radiation as a recognised source of information for a variety of applications ranging from risk assessments for human health to environmental impact studies. To achieve this, the project

- defines UV map products together with the users, in terms of coverage, content (i.e. spectral characteristics), spatial resolution, etc.
- prototypes products by customising and improving methodologies developed in the framework of several national projects.
- thoroughly assesses their quality and usefulness for the users; the validation exercise exploits ground measurements of the UV radiation performed by many laboratories in Europe and world-wide.

In this framework, the SSSA Unit develops maps that take into account the total atmospheric column ozone content, cloud cover, aerosols, surface reflectance and altitude. GOME level 3 products are used for the ozone content while the cloud optical thickness is estimated from full resolution METEOSAT data. The maps have a spatial resolution of 0.05 deg. and can be generated every half-hour. The image below represents the monthly average of the daily erythemal dose (quantifying the effect on human skin) in April 1997.

More information on the MAUVE project can be found at <http://www.nilu.no/projects/mauve/>.

POPULATION SECURITY WORKSHOP

The SSSA Unit will be hosting a workshop on the subject of "Population Security - the role of Spatial Information" on 29-30 November 1999 at the JRC Ispra.

Figure 5: Average daily erythemal dose for April 1997

The aim is to gather together interested participants to discuss proven applications that help address the policy areas in this subject. The activities of the MOLAND and Kosovo projects of the SSSA Unit of the Space Applications Institute will be presented. Ideas of topics and presentations are also welcome from interested participants.

For further information, please contact Carlo Lavalle via email: carlo.lavalle@jrc.it or fax: +39 0332 78 5461.

CORRIGENDUM

The CEO apologises for an error that was made in our recent publication 'EO for better Information - CEO Programme 1996-1998'. The contact details for the CEREAL YES shared-cost action project were incorrect. The prime contractor on this project is in fact IBERSAT SA in Spain, and the contact details should have read:

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